

METHODS OF TEACHING READING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article provides an overview of a variety of methods for teaching reading in primary schools, with an emphasis on their effectiveness and applicability. The study includes analysis of the phonetic method, the whole word method, the balanced method and the integration of technology into the educational process. The advantages of each method are given, as well as caveats about possible challenges. Particular attention is paid to creating a learning environment that encourages the development of reading skills in young students. This article provides an extensive overview of methods designed to provide balanced and innovative reading instruction in elementary schools, describes educators select the best method to suit the needs and nature of their classroom.*

Keywords: *Reading skills, primary schools, the phonetic method, the whole word method, the balanced method, Pitman's Alphabet, The Montessori method.*

One of the most important and positive changes in the field of primary education is the decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No. PQ-1875 “On further improvement of the system for studying foreign languages” based on this decision, in the 1st grade of a general education school, the study of foreign languages, mainly English, begins in the form of play-based lessons and oral speech lessons, and in the 2nd grade, step-by-step instruction in the alphabet, reading, writing and grammar begins.

Currently, numerous methods and approaches are being developed to teach English to the young generation, aligning with the demands of the times, spanning from preschool to primary grades. Ongoing research is diligently exploring practical applications of these methodologies, and the anticipated results are expected to yield valuable insights.

Teaching foreign languages to children from an early age presents myriad advantages. Foremost among these is the cultivation of a genuine love for the language, instigating a lasting interest in language acquisition. Through the process of learning a foreign language, students not only become acquainted with the linguistic nuances of another nation but also gain insights into its culture, values, and way of life. Consequently, foundational concepts and impressions about the world begin to take root in the minds of young learners.

There are several methods for teaching English reading in primary school, each suited to different learning styles and student needs. Let’s look each method in details.

1. The phonetic method. The phonetic method of teaching reading in primary school is based on the principle of establishing connections between sounds and letters or their combinations. This method seeks to develop decoding skills by allowing students to recognize and read words based on phonemes and their corresponding letters. This approach comprises two distinct directions. The first is the systematic phonetics method, where the systematic teaching of phonetics takes precedence, typically initiated, though not universally, before introducing the reading of whole words. This approach primarily relies on synthesis; children are instructed on the sounds of individual letters and engage in activities to reinforce the connection between these sounds. The second direction is the internal phonetics method, which is rooted in visual and semantic reading. In this method, the teaching of phonetics is deferred and introduced in smaller

increments. Children adopting this approach learn letter sounds through the process of dissecting and understanding familiar words.

The phonetic method includes a variety of activities and exercises for elementary school students. For example, sound cards. Teachers can use cards with pictures of objects labeled with sounds and letters. Students can match sounds with letters and then decode words. Sound cards help students make connections between phonemes (sounds) and corresponding letters.

2. The whole word method. The whole word method is based on the presentation of language as an integral system, where students learn to read and understand texts in their entirety. Instead of learning sounds and letters in isolation, students interact with texts, literature, and real-life materials. Let's give an example of activities, reading books and stories in class. Students read books and stories with the teacher, discuss the content and analyze the linguistic features of the text.

3. The balanced method. The balanced method in teaching reading is an approach that integrates elements of various methods, such as phonics, whole language and linguistic methods. The goal of the balanced method is to ensure that students develop their reading skills comprehensively and harmoniously. The principle of this method is to pay attention to sounds and letter correspondence to develop decoding skills. Students learn to recognize sounds and letters and apply this knowledge when reading words and texts.

4. "Pitman's Alphabet" is grounded in the English alphabet but extends it to encompass 44 letters. Each letter within this alphabet maintains a consistent pronunciation, ensuring that words are pronounced exactly as they are spelled. In this expanded alphabet, capital letters follow the same writing style as lowercase letters but in a larger font. As the child becomes proficient in reading, the transitional use of these letters is gradually replaced with the standard alphabet.

5. The Montessori method. The Montessori method of teaching reading offers an individualized and structured approach to developing children's reading skills. Developed by Italian physician and educator Maria Montessori, this method includes a number of unique principles and materials for developing language skills in young children. Maria Montessori provided children with the alphabet letters and guided them in recognizing, writing, and pronouncing each letter. As the children progressed and acquired the ability to blend sounds to form words, Montessori encouraged them to advance further by combining words into sentences.

Among the various methods mentioned, the two predominant approaches, whole word reading and phonics, stand out as the most commonly debated in terms of effectiveness. The ongoing discourse among proponents of these methods has yet to settle on a definitive answer.

The advantages of the whole word reading method are notable. Given the multitude of exception words in the English language that defy conventional reading rules, teaching these exceptions is inevitable. Moreover, many of these exceptions are high-frequency words, making their inclusion in the curriculum crucial. The visualization method employed in whole word reading facilitates a relatively swift initiation into meaningful reading. In contrast, the introduction of reading rules often entails a prolonged period of practicing rules with words that lack communicative significance. At this stage, the focus is primarily on adhering to a specific rule, with less emphasis on understanding the meaning of the words. Consequently, whole word reading accelerates the child's ability to read small dialogues within a mere 2-3 weeks, fostering a sense of pride and accomplishment in their English reading skills. The process of visualization learning also plays a vital role in the development of beneficial reading strategies. Notably, the approach

promotes the adoption of useful strategies like reading by keywords (e.g., "My name... is"), which proves crucial for achieving quick and fluent reading.

Conclusion

It is essential to emphasize that the acquisition of full reading skills for primary schoolchildren should be approached with simplicity and without imposing unnecessary pressure. Regardless of the chosen methods for teaching reading, the focus should be on creating an easy and unobtrusive learning experience for young learners, ensuring a positive foundation for their language development journey.

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